

ISic3546

I.Sicily inscription 3546

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stucco

Object

painted wall

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Centuripae

Place of origin (modern)

Centuripe

Provenance

Tomba no.2, Contrada Biliuzzo, Centuripe

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Centuripe, in situ

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI337198

1. M[— —]ς ἥρωϲ ἀγαθός.

2.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645621

EDCS 70900400

PHI 337198

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum*

graecum. At 52.0889

Rizza, G. 2002. Scavi e ricerche a Centuripe. Catania. At 13-14 fig.4-5

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